

6. The intergalactic Medium

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The intergalactic Medium with Galaxies

Intergalactic Medium

Galaxies

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The intergalactic Medium - Hydrogen

The space between Galaxies appears black and empty in most images, but matter is also found here - the so-called intergalactic Medium (see image). Although the average particle density in intergalactic space is so small it would be called a perfect vacuum on Earth. But in sum, intergalactic huge space results in impressive masses.

As expected, the density is higher near a Galaxy than further away from it. In the vicinity of a Galaxy, the density is typically around 0.001 particles per cubic centimeter; in a volume of 1m^3 , one would therefore find 1000 particles.

Information about the intergalactic Medium is therefore mainly provided by light and radiation that also pass through the intergalactic Medium on their way to Earth and are partially absorbed by it. This is why one sees many absorption lines when observing a bright source - typically a **Quasar** [a Quasar is the active nucleus of a Galaxy that appears almost point-like in the visible range of light].

A large part - up to 95% - of the matter in the intergalactic Medium is **hydrogen**, which was created shortly after the Big Bang 13.8 billion years ago. However, carbon, nitrogen and silicon have also been detected in the intergalactic Medium. These heavy elements can only be formed in Stars from which the intergalactic Medium is far away. Their occurrence therefore provides clues to the exchange of matter that takes place between neighbouring Galaxies. This includes, for example, bridges of hydrogen gas between the Milky Way and the Galaxies closest to it, the Magellanic clouds.

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Intergalactic gas: An extremely diluted «Atmosphere»

The intergalactic Medium (IGM), also called intergalactic gas, is hydrogen gas that is not bound to individual Galaxies but exists in the space between them (see p. 66). It consists mainly of ionised hydrogen gas H^+ , the so-called **plasma HII**; neutral hydrogen (H or HI) makes up only about one millionth of the total Medium. The IGM should not be confused with the interstellar Medium (p. 46), which is found between the Stars of Galaxies. However, the boundaries between intergalactic and interstellar Medium are fluid.

Cosmologists have long suspected that the large-scale structure of the Universe resembles a spider's web: enormous **filaments** of hydrogen gas criss-cross the dark expanse of space. They form a **branching network with nodes** where matter accumulates and **Galaxies** like our Milky Way form. However, since the diffuse gas of the cosmic filaments does not emit any light, astrophysicists predicted the existence of the intergalactic network from computer simulations only.

It is thanks to a coincidence that astronomer Sebastiano Cantalupo from the University of California in Santa Cruz and his colleagues have now been able to see part of the mysterious web for the first time. They were observing the quasar UM287 at a distance of 10 billion light years at the W. M. Keck Observatory in Hawaii when they noticed something unusual: In the images, **they found an enormous filament of hydrogen** extending into intergalactic space over a distance of almost two million light years. The enormous radiation of a quasar (see p. 66) had caused the gas to glow.

In the image on page 68 (simulation), the **filaments** of hydrogen gas and the **Galaxies** are shown as tiny dots at the nodes of the network !

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Network distribution of matter in the large-scale Universe

Filaments of
hydrogen network

Node:
Galaxy

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The Universe: Origin, Evolution and Properties

The formation of the Universe at the Big Bang (see Edwin Hubble, p. A-5-1) and its development over time are shown in the picture below. The Universe, also called the Cosmos, is the totality of space, time and all the matter and energy in it. The observable Universe, on the other hand, is limited to the detectable arrangement of all matter and energy, starting with elementary particles and extending to large-scale structures such as Galaxies and Galaxy-Clusters (see Chapters 5 and 6).

The age of the Universe has been measured very precisely by the Planck space telescope; it is 13.81 ± 0.04 Billion years. Regarding the shape, some data from the WMAP satellite suggest that the Universe is an ellipsoid.

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Referenzen – 6-1

- R-6-0 p.64: Intergalaktisches Medium – Haupttitel
- R-6-1 p. 65: Intergalaktisches Medium mitGalaxien
- a) Intergalaktisches Medium
[https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Intergalaktisches_Medium#:~:text=Als intergalaktisches Medium...](https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Intergalaktisches_Medium#:~:text=Als%20intergalaktisches%20Medium...)
 - b) Wir untersuchen die Leere: interplanetare, interstellare und intergalaktische
<https://de.great-spacing.com/publication/5610/> - Beschriftung von P. Brüesch
- R-6-2 p. 66: Das intergalaktische Medium
- a) Intergalaktisches Medium (Franziska Konitzer (23.07.2114)
<https://www.weltderphysik.de/geboet/universum-und-galaxienhaufen/intergalaktisches-medium/>
 - b) What Happens in Intergalactic Space ?
<https://www.livescience.com/69578-what-happens-in-intergalactic-space.html/>
 - c) Intergalaktische Materie - <https://abenteuer.universum.de/galaxien/inter.html>
 - d) Quasar
<https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quasar#> - Ein Quasar ist der aktive Kern einer Galaxie, der im sichtbaren Bereich des Lichtes nahezu punktförmig erscheint (wie ein Stern) und sehr grosse Energiemengen in anderen Wellenlängenbereichen ausstrahlt.
- R-6-3 p. 67: Intergalaktisches Gas: Eine extrem verdünnte «Atmosphäre»
- a) Längster intergalaktischer Gasfaden entdeckt -
<https://astro.uni-bonn.de/news/2020/12/17/G-filament>
 - b) Frankfurter Allgemeine - Der Einfluss des kosmischen Netzwerks
<https://www.faz.net/aktuell/wissen/weltraum/neuermessung-des-kosmischen-netzwerks-14995866.html>
 - c) Ein Überblick über das Arbeitsgebiet der Astrophysik II
https://www.astro.physik.uni-potsdam.de/~www/research/astro_2_de.html
 - d) Galaxy filament - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Galaxy_filament
- R-6-4 p. 68: Planck discovers filament of hot gas linking two galaxy clusters
<https://phys.org/news/2012-11-planck-filament-hot-gas-linking.html>
- R-6-5 p. 69: Das Universum: Entstehung, Entwicklung und Eigenschaften - <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Universum>

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